

pH dependent photooxygenation of xanthine and uric acid

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Abstract : Photooxygenation of xanthine and uric acid has been carried out by singlet oxygen in presence of methylene blue and rose bengal respectively in different media (neutral, acidic, alkaline) at different pH giving various products, which have been characterized by spectral data and elemental analysis.

Keywords : Xanthine, uric acid, photooxygenation, pH dependent.

Introduction

Photochemistry of organic compounds has been a vast field of research. Organic photochemistry gives us the way for new chemical reactions¹⁻³. Photooxygenation of organic substrates have been extensively studied in recent years⁴⁻¹². Singlet oxygen is known to react with different types of organic compounds, giving rise to a variety of product. The relationship between the structure of a dye and its mechanism and efficiency for photosensitization and the relationship between the chemical structure of the substrate and its rate and mechanism of photooxidation has been characteristic to their photodynamic efficiency¹³⁻¹⁵. The effect of various parameters like wave length, intensity, nature of solvent, pH etc. have also been studied¹⁶⁻²⁰.

Photooxygenation can be described as a reaction in which substrate gives initial oxygen adduct by combination with oxygen in presence of light and a sensitizer. The photooxygenation of purine represents a versatile and widely accepted tool for introducing oxygenated functions in a mild, simple and selective way^{21,22}. The photosensitized oxygenation of purines depends upon the nature of the purine bases²¹. Sensitized photooxygenation of xanthine in alkaline medium followed by acidification gives a mixture of products consisting of allantoin and triuret²⁴.

Photooxygenation of a variety of organic compounds containing the C=N bond have been reported²⁵⁻²⁷. Pu-

rimines are basic chemicals of life. A very little work has been done on photooxygenation of purines by singlet oxygen. Therefore, in the present paper we report the photooxygenation of xanthine and uric acid under different conditions, as they are important biomolecules.

Experimental

Photooxygenation of xanthine (1) in alkaline medium :

Xanthine (2.0 g) was dissolved in liquid ammonia (200 ml) in a glass beaker and the solution was transferred into the immersion well photoreactor (SAIC make). Methylene blue (0.01 g) was added as a sensitizer. The solution was then irradiated with low-pressure mercury vapour lamp, which had been placed inside the photoreactor. Air was continuously bubbled through the solution with the help of an airator. The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept constant by continuous water circulation. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC using benzene : methanol (2 : 3) solvent system, which showed a single spot initially, corresponding to the reactant. A new spot appeared on the plate after 26 h. The spot of the substrate disappeared after 38 h. Then the irradiation was stopped and the dye was removed by animal charcoal treatment. The solution was concentrated on water bath under reduced pressure and then the beaker was placed as such over night in fridge when light brown crystals appeared, which were filtered, washed with water and recrystallised with DMSO (product 2).

Photooxygenation of xanthine in neutral and acidic medium :

The solution of xanthine in *n*-butanol in neutral and acidic condition shows no change on TLC even after prolonged irradiations.

Photooxygenation of uric acid (3) in neutral medium :

Uric acid (2.0 g) was dissolved in glycerol (200 ml) in a double walled glass beaker. Rose bengal (0.01 g) was added as a sensitizer. The same procedure was adopted as mentioned in Experiment 1. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using benzene : methanol (2 : 3) solvent system, which showed a single spot initially, corresponding to the reactant. A new spot appeared on the plate after 18 h. The spot of the substrate disappeared after 23 h. The reaction mixture was worked out in the same manner as in the previous experiment. The product **4** was obtained as colourless crystals.

Photooxygenation of uric acid in acidic medium :

Uric acid (2.0 g) was dissolved in glycerol (200 ml) in a double walled glass beaker. The solution was made acidic by adding an acetic acid. Rose Bengal (0.1 g) was added as a sensitizer. The same procedure was adopted as mentioned in Experiment 1. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using benzene : methanol (2 : 3) solvent system, which showed a single spot initially, corresponding to the reactant. Two new spots appeared on the plate after 21 h. The spot of the substrate disappeared after 38 h. The reaction mixture was worked out in the same manner as in the previous experiments. The products **5** and **6** were separated by fractional crystallization. Product **5** was identified as 5-hydroxy barbituric acid and product **6** was identified as urea by co-TLC and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample.

Photooxygenation of uric acid in alkaline medium :

Uric acid (2.0 g) was dissolved in glycerol (200 ml) in a double walled glass beaker. The solution was made

alkaline by adding an alcoholic solution of NaOH. Rose Bengal (0.01 g) was added as sensitizer. The same procedure was adopted as mentioned in Experiment 1. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using benzene : methanol (2 : 3) solvent system, which showed a single spot initially, corresponding to the reactant. Two new spots appeared on the plate after 18 h. The spot of the substrate disappeared after 36 h. The reaction mixture was worked out in the same manner as in the previous experiments. The product **7** and **8** were separated by fractional crystallization. Product **8** was found to be urea by co-TLC and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample.

Results and discussion

Photooxygenation of xanthine (**1**) by singlet molecular oxygen gave the product **2** through the formation of peroxide as given below.

The structure of the product has been confirmed by spectral and elemental analysis. The results of the elemental analysis are given in Table 1 and correspond well

Table 1. Melting points, yields, elemental analysis of products **2**, **4**, **5**, **7**

Product	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :		
			Found (Calcd.)		
			C	H	N
2	308	46.11	40.12 (40.00)	1.32 (1.33)	37.35 (37.33)
4	312	74.71	35.79 (35.83)	3.47 (3.51)	20.86 (20.89)
5	222 (Lit. m.p. 224 °C)	45.11	27.89 (27.92)	2.30 (2.34)	32.49 (32.55)
7	255 (Lit. m.p. 256 °C)	72.18	33.80 (33.82)	1.38 (1.42)	19.69 (19.72)

with the calculated values. The spectral data of the product is as follows. IR : 3327 (N-H stretching), 1690 ($C=O$ stretching), 1660 cm^{-1} ($C=N$ stretching); 1H NMR : δ

Note

9.37 (2NH protons); ^{13}C NMR : δ 152.4, 157.6, 190, 170 (carbonyl carbons) and 168 (C=N carbon); Mass : *m/e* 166 (M^+ peak), 138 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CO}$), 110 ($138 - \text{N}_2$), 83 ($110 - \text{HCN}$) etc.

Uric acid (3) on irradiation in neutral medium gives product 4 as follows :

stretching), 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching) etc.; ^1H NMR : δ 7.52 (4NH protons), 4.59 (2OH protons); ^{13}C NMR : δ 190 (carbonyl carbon atoms), 155 (C-OH carbon atom); Mass : *m/e* 202 (M^+ peak), 185 ($202 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 168 ($185 - \text{OH}$), 139 ($167 - \text{CO}$), 185 ($202 - \text{OH}$), 112 ($139 - \text{HCN}$) etc.

The structure of the product has been confirmed by spectral data : IR : 3438 (O-H stretching), 3188 (N-H

Photooxygenation of uric acid in acidic medium gave 5-hydroxy barbituric acid (5) and urea (6) as follows :

Probable Mechanism

Spectral data of 5 : IR : 3471 (O–H stretching), 3149 (N–H stretching), 1700 (C=O stretching), 1647 (C=N stretching); ¹H NMR : δ 7.52 (2NH protons), 5.6 (OH proton); ¹³C NMR : δ 185 and 178 (carbonyl carbon atoms), 135 (CH–OH carbon); Mass : *m/e* 144 (M⁺ peak), 127 (144-OH), 99 (127-CO) etc.

Irradiation of uric acid in alkaline medium gives alloxan (7) and urea as follows :

In alkaline medium, the reaction is found to be slow. This may be because of the fact that the presence of OH⁻ ions may decrease the rate of dissociation of C–N bond due to the partial association with NH proton, thereby imparting a fractional –ve charge on N.

Spectral data of product 7 : IR : 3043 cm⁻¹ (N–H stretching), 1647 cm⁻¹ (C=O) etc.; ¹H NMR : δ 7.9 (2NH protons); ¹³C NMR : δ 175, 178, 182 (carbonyl carbon atoms); Mass : *m/e* 142 (M⁺ peak), 114 (142-CO), 58 (114-2CO) etc.

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